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EFFECT OF MULTIPLE TAXATION ON GROWTH OF SMES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study focused on the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. Guided by three research questions and hypotheses, a descriptive survey design was used. The population of the study consisted of 3144 registered SMEs in South Eastern Nigeria while 336 registered SMEs were sampled as determined using a simple random sampling method. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed using simple percentage, Z-test and Pearson Product Moment correlation with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social science. The findings reveal Multiple taxations has a significant negative effect on earnings and investment decisions of small and medium scale enterprise and that there is a significant relationship between excess tax charges and the survival of small and medium scale enterprise. The researcher concluded that multiple taxations have a significant negative effect on the growth of small and medium scale enterprises. The researcher recommends among others that Tax regulations governing SMEs should be simplified to make compliance easier for them. This includes clear and simple tax regulations and an undemanding tax filing process. The use of information technology should also be encouraged to enable the electronic capture of taxes paid by each SME thereby eliminating multiple taxations.

Introduction

In recent times, the world economy has developed tremendously and this has been linked to activities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), especially in developing countries. A study carried out by the Federal Office of Statistics shows that in Nigeria, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises make up 97% of productive units of the economy (Ariyo, 2005). Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) are those non-subsiary, independent firms that employ a maximum of 50-500 employees with an annual turnover / total assets of no more than 500 million nairas. The financial needs of small businesses are diverse and context-specific and, as such, microfinance banks were made available for the provision of financial services adapted to the needs of low-income people such as micro-entrepreneurs, especially the provision of small loans, acceptance of small savings deposits, and simple payments services needed by micro-entrepreneurs. However, the mortality rate of these small firms is very high. According to the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), 80% of SMEs die before their 5th anniversary. Among the factors responsible for these untimely close-ups are tax-related issues, ranging from multiple taxations to enormous tax burdens among other issues (Yusuf, 2014).

However, Holban (2017) posits that taxation can contribute to development and welfare through three sources; It must be able to generate sufficient funds for financing public services and social transfers at a

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE MANAGEMENT

high level of quality, it should offer an incentive for more employment and efficient and lasting use of natural resources, finally, it should be able to reallocate income. But in the case of SMEs, the tax must be imposed in such a way that puts their income and need for survival into consideration. It is expedient that enough profit is allowed them to expand their businesses. The tax policy must be one that will not encourage SMEs to remain in the informal sector or to evade or avoid tax payments. More so, many small firms in Africa, including Nigeria, choose to remain in the informal sector because the perceived benefits outweigh the perceived costs (Sumathi, 2012).

Multiple taxations, on the other hand, is the imposition of different types of taxes that could have come under one major tax form on the people by the government (Taiwo & Falohun, 2016). In Nigeria, SMEs have not performed commendably well as they have not adequately played the expected significant role in the economic growth of the nation (Taiwo & Falohun, 2016). These small enterprises have progressively been recognized as enterprises that add considerably to the creation of jobs, economic growth and eradication of poverty in Africa in which Nigeria is not an exception. However, these small and medium enterprises face difficulties when dealing with the government in general and the tax administration in particular. Some of these difficulties could be attributed to multiple and outrageous tax rates (Baurer, 2015).

Different related studies were reviewed, but none of the studies focused on the effects of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria concerning their earnings, survival and investment decision. While some past studies focused on a particular state or a selected particular industry, (Adebisi&Gbegi, 2013; Okpalaojiego&Okolo, 2016; Yamoah, Arthur, &Issaka, 2014), their outcome cannot be generalized. This study intends to fill this gap by covering a wider scope, the Southeast states of Nigeriawhich comprise Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states focusing on the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria concerning earnings, survival and investment decision.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. ascertain the effect of multiple taxations on earnings of small and medium scale enterprise
2. investigate the relationship between excess tax charges and survival of small and medium scale enterprise
3. assess the effect of multiple taxations on investment decisions of small and medium scale enterprise

The following null hypotheses guided the study

H_{01} : Multiple taxations do not affect earnings of small and medium scale enterprise

H_{02} : There is no relationship between excess tax charges and survival of small and medium scale enterprise

H_{03} : Multiple taxations do not affect the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise.

Scope of the Study

This study is delimited to the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The study focused on the entire registered SMEs operating in the five South Eastern states of Nigeria only.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Tax

Tax is a compulsory contribution to government revenue, levied by the government on workers' income and business profits, or added to the cost of some goods, services, and transactions.

According to Njoku (2009), Tax is compulsory contributions or payments of money or occasionally of goods and services from private individuals, institutions or groups to the governments for the defraying

of expenditures incurred by the government in the common interest of all without reference to any special benefit conferred on any of the person or impersonal unit that made the compulsory contributions or payments. Taxes may be levied by different levels of government, and the inclusion of "compulsory" serves to remind us that evasion is punishable by law. It is also a payment exacted by legislative authority. Bhatia (2009), defined tax as a compulsory levy payable by an economic unit to the government without any corresponding entitlement to receive a definite direct quid pro quo from the government.

Multiple Taxation

According to Adebayo, Balogun and Kareem (2013), multiple taxation is a phenomenon that describes an income that is subjected to tax more than once, often by two or more different authorities in a way that may be unfair or illegal. Illegality and unfairness distinguish multiple taxations from double taxation. The former often have the characteristics of being unfair and also illegal. Multiple taxations about a company or individual is a situation where the same profit or income which is liable for tax in Nigeria has been respectively subjected to tax by another tax authority in Nigeria or another country outside Nigeria (Adebisi&Gbegi, 2013).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

The term 'small and medium enterprises' describes a group of business organisations that are especially heterogeneous as they embrace a broad varied form ranging from hotels, manufacturing industries, agriculture, restaurants, computer software firms and small machine shops among many others (Asaolu, Oladoyin, & Oladele, 2015). According to Nnanna (2012), the sole aim of the introduction of the concept of small and medium enterprises into the development scenery was to perk up trade and industrialization in today's developed nations. The small and medium enterprise definitions are drawn from each country based on the policies, agencies, programs and institutions, and the role of SMEs in the economy (Abdullah, 2000; Etuk, Etuk&Baghebo, 2014).

According to existing studies, the characterization of SMEs varies in different economies although the core concept is similar (Adeyemi 2011; Ajayi, 2000; Ogechukwu, Oboreh, Umokoro & Uche, 2013). According to Okonkwo and Obidike (2016), the meaning given to small and medium enterprises differs by country, schools, context, scholars and author. In some countries, SMEs are defined by their yearly turnover and number of staff. In other countries, SMEs are defined in terms of the industry and nature of businesses (Ibrahim, 2015). Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile- Ife, Centre for Industrial Research and Development (CIRD) classified small scale business as an enterprise that has a working capital base not below and not higher than #250,000 and employing not more than 50 workers on a full-time basis. In 2005, the credit guiding principle to the commercial banks by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) classified small scale enterprises as a business whose annual turnover is below and not higher than #500,000, while the Merchant banks were considered businesses with capital investment less than #2,000,000 (the cost of land not included) or turnover up to but not higher than 5million Naira as small scale businesses (Solomon, 2011). The Federal Ministry of Commerce and Industries cited in Olabisi, Olagbemi, and Atere (2011), classified SMEs as a firm whose total investment (with the exclusion of the cost of land, however with capital included) is close to #750,000 and the maximum number of 50 persons as employees.

According to the National Council of Industries (2009), small and medium scale enterprises are business enterprises whose overall costs with land excluded is #200,000,000 or less. The National Council of Industry (2001) defined small and medium enterprises as businesses with between 11 and 100 employees or a total cost of N50 million or less, together with working capital and exclusive of the cost of land. While, Medium Scale Enterprise is an enterprise with a labour size of between 101-300 personnel or a total cost of over N50 million but not higher than N200 million, together with working capital but without including the cost of land (Aremu, 2011). The Third National Development Plan in Nigeria described SME

as a business that employs not up to ten workers and the asset investment does not go beyond #600,000 (Ogechukwu, 2011).

Below is a schematic representation of the conceptual framework of the study

Figure 1: Source: Researcher's Innovation (2019)

Theoretical framework

This study is hinged on Three Sigma's Theory of the Business Model. This model is an application of Peter Drucker's theory of the business. The essential belief of this theory is that lots of business organisations decline and fail for the reason that the suppositions they formulate that form the root for their basic business decisions become obsolete or invalid (Whittington, 2002). For this cause, all businesses and organizations must, from time to time, observe their basic suppositions to find out whether they persist to reflect on the existing realities they combat and also how they should modify them just in case they do not. This model enables the organization to discover and inspect those suppositions and amend them if required. This model is appropriate for the use of businesses, governments, and non-profit organizations. It can as well be used for new business startups to spot, look at, and formulate precise assumptions that will be the cause of their business planning. The model has three divisions with each one holding one or more components that present a framework to analyze what went before and current decisions (Ezenwa, 2016).

The first division is the organisational focus, which necessitates that strategic thinking starts with a reassessment of the organisation's mission, vision, and purpose, and the examination of these components for sensibleness and reliability to spot inherent and precise suppositions that affect a decision on whether to enter or remain in the business enterprise activity.

The second division of this model has to do with the external environment and contains five components. The first component obliges the enterprise to analyse the social, economic, and political factors in the external business environment to establish the precise suppositions regarding them that influence the business's decisions, and its activities. The second component emphasises market factors such as existing and potential customers, distribution channel, advertisement, promotion, pricing, product distinctiveness, and among others, which require strategic thinking to find out the relevant suppositions on them that

influence the business decisions.

The third component of this division reflects on the users of the enterprise: product, and calls for the firm to evaluate the factors of its customer behaviour which include the firm's product purchase decision, influences on the purchase or use of the product and so on, to find out customers' characteristics that influence the decision and expectations of the business organisation. The fourth component obliges the firm to study the technological factors of the business environment to find out the causal features of the technological environmental factors that influence the firm's decisions and expectations.

Lastly, the fifth component dwells on the industry's competitive formation and necessitates the need for the business organisation to examine this formation to determine the competitive formation feature that influences the business decisions. This structure includes the potential new entrants into the market, suppliers, substitute products, market segment products, and major competitors. The competitive industry factors which pose the greatest threat must be neutralized by taking strategic actions.

The third division of this business model is footed on the competitive advantage and core competencies of an enterprise. It stressed the need for an enterprise to examine organisational competencies. The second division of the business model provides a theoretical base for this study as it shows that external environmental factors necessitate the need for a business enterprise, including SMEs to operate strategically to survive and boost effectiveness in their performance in a most efficient manner. The business/owners need to be cognizant of what influence the external environmental factors can pose on their business operation and how the comprehension of their effects make for optimal performance.

Empirical Review

Nwoye (2014) carried out a study on financing small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) as a challenge for entrepreneurial development in Abia State in Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions and an ex post facto research design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 711 registered SMEs operating in Abia state. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to draw a sample from the population and 170 SMEs were sampled. The study generated primary data collected through a structured questionnaire. Out of one hundred and seventy (170) questionnaires distributed, one hundred and Sixty-five (165) were returned and analyzed. The findings show that financing small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) has a significant effect on the development of SMEs.

Olowe, Moradeyo and Babalola (2013) examined the impact of Microfinance Bank on Small and Medium Growth in Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions and a descriptive research design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of the entire registered SMEs in Oyo State which amounted to 1289 SMEs. However, the study was restricted to the Ibadan metropolis. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the participating SMEs. A simple random sampling technique was used to select a total of 82 SME operators that constituted the sample size. Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The results showed that financial services obtained from Microfinance Bank have a positive significant impact on SMEs growth in Nigeria. The results also revealed that the duration of the loan has a positive impact on SMEs' growth but was not statistically significant. The results also showed that high-interest rates, collateral security and frequency of loan repayment can cripple the expansion of SMEs in Nigeria. The study recommended that Microfinance Bank should lighten the condition for borrowing and increase the duration of their customers' loans and also spread the repayment over a long period.

Yamoah, Arthur and Issaka (2014) carried out a study on the relationship between multiple taxes and the Growth of SMEs in Nigeria's Economy. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE MANAGEMENT

study consisted of 2344 SMEs. Primary data was generated through a structured questionnaire and were analysed using simple percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation with the aid of a statistical package for social sciences. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between Tax Policy and the Growth of SMEs in Nigeria's Economy.

On the other hand, Lugo's (2014) findings are studied how tax policy affects entrepreneurship in Canada showed that cutting taxes to improve entrepreneurial activities is not the most effective way. The research findings suggested that fostering economic growth might be a better alternative to accomplish improvement in entrepreneurial outcomes in Canada.

The results obtained from the study conducted by Kagame (2014) on the analysis of tax policy and its effect on small businesses and entrepreneurial enterprises in Uganda revealed that taxation (high taxes and poor taxation policy consequentially reduced the capital base of SMEs and also hindered the performance of entrepreneurial enterprises in the country.

Isaac (2015) investigated the effects of government taxation policy on UasinGishu County, Kenya, SMEs sales revenue. The study adopted an exploratory research design. The data for the study were generated from secondary and primary sources; the primary data were extracted by administering 180 questionnaires, personal interviews and document analysis. The research findings showed that government tax policy has a direct significant impact on SME sales revenue. Furthermore, the study revealed that the effects of government taxation policy on SME sales revenue could either be positive or negative. The study concluded that the SMEs should be levied a lower amount of tax payable to allow for them to have as much necessary funds for other activities that will lead to growth in their business and yield profitability.

Anochie and Ude (2015) empirically evaluated the performance of the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) Equity Investment Scheme in Nigeria (SMEEIS), the study tried to look into different sources of funds available to small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. The study also looked at the importance of small and medium enterprises in an economy like Nigeria's and its comparison to other economies in some countries. It was observed that small and Medium Enterprises are known as pioneers of industrialization to this extent, they employ a high number of employees and also are the determinant of the economic growth of a nation, hence, the need for financing them for efficiency and effectiveness. The panacea for problems of economic growth in developing countries has been the centrepiece of industrial development in many countries like Nigeria. The Banking sector of the economy for this purpose tries to solve some of the problems associated with small and medium scale industries. Therefore the study looked into the effectiveness of the Small and Medium Enterprise Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS) as per the initiative of the banker's committee. It also considered the views of other scholars, the bankers' committee act and also problems facing small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. Moreover, it delved into the various schemes available to small and medium enterprises with a critical view of the scheme under study (small and medium enterprise equity investment scheme). It found that the program/scheme failed as a result of many factors one of which was that the initiators of the scheme were the beneficiaries. It, therefore, concluded that the aim of the scheme was not actualized as a result of conditions given by the bankers' committee as per eligibility and other factors like infrastructure, communication facilities, lack of technology, literacy level, stiff competition from Multinational Corporations (MNCs) and Lack of steady power.

Ugwuoba (2015) carried out a study on financing small and medium-scale enterprises for sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and a descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 244 registered SMEs and 100 were sampled using simple random sampling. Primary data were used collected through structure and were

analyzed using simple percentage, arithmetic mean and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the aid of a statistical package for social science (SPSS, 20). The findings showed that Economic growth and development cannot be achieved without putting in place well-focused programmes to create employment opportunities, generation of income and reduction in poverty through SMEs.

On the same trend, the study conducted by Okolo, Okpaloa, and Okolo (2016) revealed that multiple taxes hurt SME investment. And they also concluded that a noteworthy association exists between SMEs investment and their capacity to pay tax.

Gulani and Usma (2016) investigated financing small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) as a challenge for entrepreneurial development in Gombe State. The study was guided by two research questions and a descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 311 registered SMEs operating in Gombe state. However, purposive and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to draw a sample from the population and 90 SMEs were sampled. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire. Out of ninety (90) questionnaires distributed, Sixty-five (65) were returned and analyzed using simple percentage, arithmetic mean and one-way analysis of variance with the aid of a statistical package for social science (SPSS, 20). The result of the analysis revealed that: Though there is no significant difference in the difficulties SMEs face when accessing finance from various sources, there is a significant difference in the level of awareness of Micro Finance Institutes by SMEs. The research, however, recommended that government policy of initiating various intervention funds for entrepreneurial development should be encouraged; SMEs in the state should be sensitized to the activities of Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs).

Summary of Literature Review and Gap in Literature

This study focused on the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The study reviewed the meaning of tax, small and medium scale, double taxation and multiple taxations. The study was anchored on Three Sigma's Theory of the Business Model. Different related studies were reviewed, but none of the studies focused on the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria concerning the effect of multiple taxations on the earnings of small and medium scale enterprises, the relationship between excess taxation and the survival of small and medium scale enterprise and impact of multiple taxations on investment decision of small and medium scale enterprises. Also, the results of previous studies are still conflicting about the direction of the relationship and effect of multiple taxations on SMEs growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, existing studies which are most related to the current Study are notably out of date. Most of the past studies were focused on a particular state or company and the outcome of the study of one state or company cannot be generalized.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The researcher chose this method because it is a very valuable and effective tool for assessing the opinions of respondents, especially in establishing cause and effect relationships in a study of this nature.

Sources of Data

The researcher used primary sources for data collection. Primary data were sourced through the use of a structured questionnaire that was administered to the respondents.

The population of the Study

The population of this study is the entire registered SMEs operating in the five states in the South East of Nigeria. Given the paucity of exact statistics, the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria SMEDAN (2017) estimated the total number of SME operators in South-East Nigeria to be 3144. This figure does not include SMEs that operate in the informal sector.

Sample Frame

State	Number	Percentage of Total
Abia	601	19.20
Anambra	943	30.28
Enugu	531	17.05
Imo	592	19.01
Ebonyi	477	15.31
Total	3144	100.00

Source: SMEs Adapted from SMEDAN, 2019

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample frame for this study is determined from the population of registered SMEs as published by SMEDAN (2017). Given the population of about 3144 SMEs in the South-East zone, Taro Yamane's formula (Yamane 1967) for sample size determination was employed to reduce the number to a manageable size.

Taro Yamane's formula (Yamane 1967) for sample size determination is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = the relevant population sought or sample size

N=Total population

e=Limit of tolerable error

1=Constant

$$= \frac{3144}{1+3144(0.05)^2}, \quad n = \frac{3144}{1+3144(0.0025)}, \quad n = 354.87 \approx 355.$$

Sharing the obtained sample size among the various states in the South-East zone, the proportional allocation technique was used to ensure that none of these participating units is cheated: The relevant formula goes thus:

$$ns = \frac{N_p \times n}{N}$$

ns = the sample size allocated to each unit

Np = the population size of each unit

n = the total sample size

N = the total population size

The resulting sample allocations are presented in table 3.1 below.

Population and Sample

Table 3.1 Distribution of Small and Medium Enterprises in South-East Nigeria

State	Number	Percentage of Total	Sample of each population
Abia	601	19.20	68
Anambra	943	30.28	106
Enugu	531	17.05	60
Imo	592	19.01	67
Ebonyi	477	15.31	54
Total	3144	100.00	355

Source: SME Adapted from SMEDAN, 2019

The respondents are to be selected from the list of the SME operators for the various states at the zonal

office of SMEDAN, Enugu a process of simple random sampling.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument used to collect data for the attainment of the study objectives was the questionnaire which was structured into two sections (A and B). Section A was structured to obtain information on the socio-economic profiles of the SMEs such as year of establishment, educational attainment of the owner(s), years of registration with SMEDAN and personal data of respondents, While section B was structured to answer the various core research issues. The questionnaire was based on a five-point Likertscale of Strongly Agree (SA)-5, Agree (A)-4,Undecided (UN).-3, Disagree (D)-2, Strongly Disagree(SD)-1,

Administration and Collection of Data gathering instrument

The researcher is not familiar with the terrain of the area under study, for this reason, there researcher used five trained enumerators in collaboration with SMEDAN officers at Enugu and the other state capitals in the South East. These enumerators were trained on how to administer the instrument, especially on how to guide the respondents who have little or no knowledge of how to fill the questionnaire appropriately.

Validation of Instrument Used

Validity of the measuring instrument refers to the degree to which the instrument measures what it is supposed to measure, The measuring instrument used in this study (the questionnaire) was carefully designed in a way that enabled the researcher to elicit opinionated, factual and interpretive information pertinent to the purpose and objectives of this study. To ensure that the validity of the measuring instrument is maximized, the researcher avoided ambiguous questions. Questions were made short, easy to understand and solicited objective answers from all respondents. To authenticate the validity of the instrument, copies of the questionnaire were given to three research experts in the Faculties of Management and Education at the University of Benin, Benin City to make their input and contributions. Their views were appropriately reflected in the instrument.

Reliability of Data

Reliability is concerned with the degree to which a test instrument consistently measures what it measures. To test the reliability of the research instrument, the researcher used Cronbach Alpha. Therefore, 20 copies of the research instrument were administered to 20 SMEs in Onitsha North LGA. Their responses were subjected to the Cronbach Alpha test at a 5% level of significance with a conventional threshold of 0.6. That is, the instrument was reliable if the Cronbach coefficient is higher than the threshold of 0.6. The tool (Cronbach Alpha) is capable of detecting the strength of each item in the research tool and the possibility of removing unnecessary items in the research tool.

The outcome was subjected to a reliability test and the result is presented in the table below:

Table 3.3: Reliability Statistics Result

Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.807	.801	12

Source: SPSS version 20.

The above result revealed that the Alpha level of 0.824 is greater than the threshold of 0.6. This indicated a high level of internal consistency of the research instrument; as such, the research instrument was declared to be highly reliable to obtain data for decision making.

Method of Data Analyses.

The researcher applied descriptive statistics such as simple percentages; mean and frequency distribution

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE MANAGEMENT

to analyze the specific objectives of the study. Inferential statistics were used to test the formulated hypotheses. Hypotheses 1, and 3, were tested using Z-test while hypothesis 2 was tested using Pearson product-moment correlation with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 23) The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (*r*) assesses the degree that quantitative variables are linearly related in a sample.

The correlation formula is given below:

$$r^2 = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{(n \sum x^2 - \sum(x)^2)(n \sum y^2 - \sum(y)^2)}$$

$$0 < r^2 < 1$$

In this study, *r*² is used to determine the relationship between the sub-variables.

The Z-test formula is

$$Z = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{s/\sqrt{n}}$$

Where \bar{x} = Sample mean

μ = Population mean

n = Sample size

n - 1 = Degree of freedom

Decision Rule: Accept the alternative hypothesis when the probability value is less than alpha otherwise reject. All the analyses will be tested at an alpha level of 0.05.

Data presentation and Analysis

Table 4.1 Analysis of Distributed Questionnaire

Questionnaire	Number of Respondents	Percentages
Distributed Questionnaire	355	-
Returned Questionnaire	336	95
Unreturned/uncompleted Questionnaire	19	5
Total	355	100

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Table 4.1 above, shows that 95 per cent of the distributed copies of the questionnaire were completed and returned while 5 per cent of the distributed copies of the questionnaire were not returned. This shows that the percentage of the returned questionnaire was very high.

Table 4.2 Response to the evaluation of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria

S/N	Multiple taxation and earnings	S	A	A	D	S	D	U	T o t a l
1	Multiple taxations significantly affect the earnings of SMEs	200(60%)	99(29%)	10(3%)	15(5%)	5 (2%)			336(100%)
2	Tax Collectors Consider Size of Business	186(55%)	108(32%)	22(7%)	16(5%)	4 (1%)			336(100%)
3	There is a relationship between SMEs sizes and ability to pay taxes	160(48%)	137(41%)	28(8%)	7 (2%)	4 (1%)			336(100%)
4	Multiple taxations affect the ability of	99(29%)	200(60%)	5 (2%)	28(8%)	5 (2%)			336(100%)

	SMEs to break even						
	Multiple taxations and SME survival						
5	Excess taxation reduces the survival of small and medium scale enterprise	155(46%)	127(38%)	42(13%)	12(4%)		336(100%)
6	Multiple Taxation Affects the Growth and Survival of SMEs Negatively in Nigeria	167(50%)	138(41%)	23(7%)	8 (2 %)		336(100%)
7	Multiple taxations affect the liquidity level of SMEs	123(37%)	119(35%)	23(7%)	55(16%)	16(5%)	336(100%)
8	Multiple taxations encourage taxpayers to evade tax	166(50%)	110(32%)	33(10%)	12(4%)	15(4%)	336(100%)
	Multiple Taxation and Investment Decision						
9	Multiple taxations significantly affect the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise	156(46%)	133(40%)	18(5%)	21(6%)	8 (2 %)	336(100%)
10	Multiple taxations frustrate investment of SMEs	134(40%)	116(49%)	33(10%)	19(6%)	34(10%)	336(100%)
11	A high rate of tax discourage employment	200(60%)	99(29%)	10(3%)	15(5%)	5 (2 %)	336(100%)
12	Multiple taxations slow down the growth projections of SMEs	186(55%)	108(32%)	22(7%)	16(5%)	4 (1 %)	336(100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

From the analysis in Table 4.2 above, it shows that 60 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations significantly affects the earnings of SMEs, 29 per cent agree, 3 per cent disagree, 5 per cent strongly disagree while 2 per cent of the respondent were undecided. The analysis shows that 55 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that tax Collectors Consider the Size of Business, 32 per cent agree, 7 per cent disagree, 5 per cent strongly disagree while 1 per cent of the respondent were undecided that tax Collectors Consider the Size of Business. Also, the analysis shows that 48 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that there is a relationship between SMEs Sizes and the Ability to Pay Taxes, 41 per cent agree, 8 per cent disagree, 2 per cent strongly disagree while 1 per cent of the respondent were undecided. The analysis shows that 29 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations affect the ability of SMEs to break even, 60 per cent agree, 2 per cent disagree, 2 per

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE MANAGEMENT

cent were undecided while 8 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple taxations affect the ability of SMEs to break even. The analysis shows that 46 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Excess taxation reduces the survival of small and medium scale enterprises, 38 per cent agree, 13 per cent disagree, while 4 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Excess taxation reduces the survival of small and medium scale enterprise. The analysis shows that 50 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple Taxation affects the Growth and Survival of SMEs Negatively in Nigeria, 41 per cent agree, 7 per cent disagree, while 2 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple Taxation affects the Growth and Survival of SMEs Negatively in Nigeria.

Also, the analysis shows that 37 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations affect the liquidity level of SMEs, 35 per cent agree, 7 per cent disagree, 5 per cent were undecided while 16 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple taxations affect the liquidity level of SMEs. Also, the analysis shows that 50 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations encourage taxpayers to evade tax, 32 per cent agree, 10 per cent disagree, 4 per cent were undecided while 4 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple taxations encourage taxpayers to evade tax. Also, the analysis shows that 46 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations significantly affect the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprises, 40 per cent agree, 5 per cent disagree, 2 per cent were undecided while 6 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple taxations significantly affect the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprises. Also, the analysis shows that 40 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that Multiple taxations frustrate the investment of SMEs, 49 per cent agree, 10 per cent disagree, 10, were undecided while 6 per cent of the respondents strongly disagree that Multiple taxations frustrate investment of SMEs. From the analysis in Table 4.2 above, it shows that 60 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that the High rate of tax discourages employment, 29 per cent agree, 3 per cent disagree, 5 per cent strongly disagree while 2 per cent of the respondent were undecided. The analysis shows that 55 per cent of the respondents strongly agree that multiple taxations slow down the growth projections of SMEs, 32 per cent agree, 7 per cent disagree, 5 per cent strongly disagree while 1 per cent of the respondent was undecided that multiple taxations slow down the growth projections of SMEs.

Test of Hypotheses using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Z-Test with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 23)

Decision rule: We accept the null hypothesis when the probability value is greater than the alpha value, otherwise, we reject it.

Significant level = 0.05

Hypotheses I

H_0 : Multiple taxations has no significant effect on earnings of small and medium scale enterprise

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Multiple taxations and SME earnings	5	73.200	64.7700	8.00	222.00

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Z-Test)

		Multiple taxations and SME earnings
N		5
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	73.200
	Std. Deviation	64.7700
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.129
	Positive	.129
	Negative	-.0889
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.971
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.002

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

The analysis above shows that the probability value (0.002) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis and conclude that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the earnings of small and medium scale enterprises

Hypotheses II

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between excess tax charges and the survival of small and medium scale enterprises.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Excess tax charges	73.2000	64.8800	5
Survival of SMEs	73.2000	65.0009	5

Correlations

		Excess tax charges	Survival of SMEs
Excess tax charges	Pearson Correlation	1	.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.021
	N	5	5
Survival of SMEs	Pearson Correlation	0.84	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	
	N	5	5

From the analyses above, it shows that the probability value (0.021) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher, therefore, reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between excess tax charges and the survival of small and medium scale enterprise with a correlation value of 0.84.

Hypotheses III

H_0 : Multiple taxations have no significant effect on the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise.

.Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum

.Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Multiple taxations and investment decisions of SME	5	73.200	64.7700	4.00	204.00

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Z-Test)

		Multiple taxations and investment decisions of SME
N		5
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	73.200
	Std. Deviation	70.770
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.129
	Positive	.129
	Negative	-.239
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.492
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.030

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

The analysis above shows that the probability value (0.030) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher, therefore, accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise.

Discussion of Findings

The following findings were revealed and discussed in this study.

Discussion of Result from a test of hypothesis I

In the course of testing hypothesis one, the analysis revealed that the probability value (0.002) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the development of small and medium scale enterprise. This was in line with the study carried out by Bello (2015) that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the development of small and medium scale enterprises. This outcome is also in line with the studies of Adebisi and Gbegi (2013), Isaac (2015), and Yamoah, Arthur, and Isiala (2014).

Discussion of Results from a test of hypothesis II

The analysis in hypothesis two shows that there is a significant relationship between excess tax charges and the survival of small and medium scale enterprises with a correlation value of 0.84. This was in line with the findings of Ocheni and Grenade (2015). Holban (2007), in his study, found that a high tax rate is a major factor affecting the growth of SMEs. Other studies in line with our results include Kagame (2014) and Ojochogwu (2012).

Discussion of Results from a test of hypothesis III

In testing the third hypothesis, the analysis shows that the probability value (0.030) is less than the alpha value (0.05): the researcher therefore accepts the alternative hypothesis and concludes that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise. This was to the study carried out by Abimbola (2011) that Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the

investment decision of small and medium scale enterprises. This is further in line with the results of Okpaloa and Okolo (2016) and Ramalho and Shelter (2009).

Summary of findings

The following findings were made from the Analyses:

1. Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the earnings of small and medium scale enterprises. ($P - value = 0.002 < 0.05$, *confident interval*; 0.05)
2. There is a significant relationship between excess tax charges and the survival of small and medium scale enterprises. ($P - value = 0.02 < 0.05$, $r = 0.84 > 0.807$; 0.05)
3. Multiple taxations have a significant effect on the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprises. ($P - value = 0.030 < 0.05$, *confident interval*; 0.05)

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in South Eastern states of Nigeria. The researcher concluded that Multiple taxations have a significant negative effect on the growth of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. This outcome implies that multiple taxations contributed greatly to the failure of SMEs as the different tax charges levied constitute reductions to profit which could be reinvested to ensure continuous growth of SMEs.

Based on the findings made from this study, the following recommendations are therefore made:

1. Tax regulations governing SMEs should be simplified to make compliance easier for them. This includes clear and simple tax regulations and an undemanding tax filing process. The use of information technology should be encouraged.
2. Tax administrators should carry out their duties more efficiently with the most care and integrity as this will help combat issues of multiple taxes.
3. Tax administrators should improve their support services towards SMEs for example, small business owners should be educated on issues of taxes computations and deduction as they are expected to pay and the incentives and exemptions they are eligible for.

The outcome of this study should be taken with caution. First, the challenge of paucity of material encountered limits the extent of coverage of the research work. The study is also limited by the challenge of data collection as some of the SMEs and government agencies found it very difficult to release some relevant information that would have added more value to the study tagged confidential, releasing such without proper approval attracts severe punishment.

In future, other researchers might wish to consider more Small and Medium Scale enterprises to increase the sample size to minimize biases. Again, interested researchers should consider the assessment of the role of tax in the growth of the SMEs sector in Nigeria by focusing on different contexts; and the perception of tax authorities / regulatory bodies of the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria.

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**Appendix 1
Questionnaire**

Dear Respondent,

I am Augustine Odion, a PhD student in the Department of Accountancy, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State.

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study, Effect of multiple taxations on the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The below statements in (Section B) require you to respond to them according to how you feel about them as well as provide basic information about yourself in (Section A). There are no rights or wrong answers. Please feel free to provide your honest opinions about the statements made. Remember that your answers are completely anonymous.

Instruction: Please kindly tick [] the option that best suit your response.

SECTION A: Demographic Information of the Respondent.

1. Sex: Male [] Female []
2. Age Bracket: 18-25yrs [] 26-33yrs [] 34-41yrs [] 42-49yrs [] 50-57yrs [] 58-65 [] 66yrs and above []
3. Highest educational attainment: FSLC [] SSCE [] OND/NCE [] B.Sc./HND [] MASTERS [] PHD. [] OTHERS []
4. Geopolitical Region: South East []
5. Occupation: FARMER [] TRADER [] CIVIL SERVANT [] PROFESSIONAL [] OTHERS [] .
6. State of Origin: Abia [] Anambra [] Ebonyi [] Enugu [] Imo []

SECTION B: Evaluation of Multiple Taxation on Growth of SMEs in Nigeria.

	Multiple taxation and earnings	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	Multiple taxations significantly affect the earnings of SMEs					
2	Tax Collectors Consider Size of Business					
3	There is a relationship between SMEs sizes and ability to pay taxes					
4	Multiple taxations affect the ability of SMEs to break even					
	Multiple taxations and SME survival	SD	A	U	D	SD
5	Excess taxation reduces the survival of small and medium scale enterprise					
6	Multiple Taxation Affects the Growth and Survival of SMEs					

	Negatively in Nigeria					
7	Multiple taxations affect the liquidity level of SMEs					
8	Multiple taxations encourage taxpayers to evade tax					
	Multiple Taxation and Investment Decision	SD	A	U	D	SD
9	Multiple taxations significantly affect the investment decision of small and medium scale enterprise					
10	Multiple taxations frustrate investment of SMEs					
11	A high rate of tax discourage employment					
12	Multiple taxations slow down the growth projections of SMEs					

13. Please kindly tell us any other thing(s) you may wish us to know about the effect of multiple taxations on the growth of Small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria.

